

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Iraq

WP8 – Country Survey Report

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Principal Investigator of the Iraqi Team

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List of Abbreviations

AVR	Assisted Voluntary Return Program
CPA	Coalition Provisional Authority
EU	European Union
ETTC	European Technology and Training Centre
HHRO	Hammurabi Human Rights Organization
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IQR	Interquartile Range
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NRM	National Referral Mechanism
SD	Standard Deviation
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

About the GAPS

GAPS is a Horizon Europe Project that focuses on the drivers of return policies and the barriers/enablers in international cooperation on returns. The project aims to address the disparities between the anticipated outcomes of return policies and their actual results by challenging the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” Specifically, GAPS:

1. Identifies the missing link in the EU’s return policy, considering both its internal and external dimensions.
2. Explores factors that facilitate or hinder international cooperation.
3. Illuminate returnees’ experiences and sheds light on the factors that shape their resilience, aspirations and hope in the face of adversities.

The GAPS project is structured into 11 Work Packages, each designed to critically examine the existing legal, policy, and institutional frameworks governing return and reintegration processes. These Work Packages aim to identify best practices, uncover structural and operational gaps, and strengthen the overall effectiveness of return governance and management by generating evidence on returnees’ lived experiences, resilience, and hope in the face of mounting adversities. Using a field survey-based approach, the project generated evidence-based insights to inform more coherent, equitable, and sustainable return policies.

GAPS fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece, and Iraq. This country report has been compiled in the context of the GAPS Work Package Eight (WP8) on ‘Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Iraq.’

WP8: Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Iraq

The WP8 focuses on the experiences of returnees in four countries: Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunisia – this report focuses on Iraq. By conducting representative surveys across these contexts, the objective is to gain a deeper understanding of returnees’ aspirations and motivations, as well as the challenges they face during and after their return. To achieve this, the study employed standardised measurement tools, including the Hope Scale, Resilience Scale, and Depression Scale. These tools allow us to assess the psychological well-being of returnees and examine how broader societal (e.g., community support, social inclusion) and structural factors (e.g., access to services, legal documentation, employment opportunities) influence their ability to cope with adversity. Ultimately, the aim is to identify patterns of vulnerability and strength among returnees and to provide evidence to inform policies and interventions that support sustainable reintegration.

1. Country Context: Iraq

The number of Iraqis abroad is estimated at approximately two million (Forced Migration Review, 2007). Statistics indicate that 58,000 people have returned to Iraq over the past seven years (United Nations, 2025). Between May 2018 and August 2020, 23,457 returnees were recorded (Displacement Tracking Matrix, 2020). Seventy-three per cent of Iraqi returnees returned from two countries: 44% from Turkey and 29% from Syria (Displacement Tracking Matrix, 2019).

There are 130,460 Iraqi refugees in Germany (Integral Human Development, 2020). The number of asylum seekers in Germany is 2,100, in the Netherlands 2,800, in Sweden 9,000, and in Greece 1,400 (Forced Migration Review, 2007). Large numbers of Iraqis remain in neighbouring countries to this day. For example, Jordan hosts about 750,000 Iraqi migrants (Forced Migration Review, 2007).

Since 1921, Iraq has experienced recurring forced displacements driven by political repression, war, sectarian violence, and climate change. Major episodes include state repression and persecution notably of minorities, including Assyrian Christians and Fayli Kurds, the Iran-Iraq war (Arab reform net, 2021), the Gulf war (Migration Policy Institute, 2008), the United States invasion of Iraq in 2003 (Shiban A., 2017), and the Islamic State of Iraq and Sham's (ISIS) takeover of parts of northern Iraq (Al-Jazeera TV, 2021). Each wave of conflict, war, and sectarian violence forced hundreds of thousands of Iraqis into forced displacements.

1.1. The Institutional and Legal Structure of Return Migration Governance in Iraq

Established after 2003, the Ministry of Migration and Displacement is the primary authority responsible for the affairs of internally displaced persons, refugees, and returnees. The Ministry plays an important role in issuing legislation to encourage the return of skilled Iraqi migrants to the country, granting them the privileges stipulated in Government Resolution No. 441 of 14 December 2008.

The National Referral Mechanism (NRM) under the Migration and Displacement Ministry serves as a model for Iraq's current return infrastructure. It was adopted by Iraqi Prime Minister Mohammed Shia al-Sudani in 2023 as part of his government's program, in which he emphasised the importance of the return of displaced persons and refugees to their places of origin. This mechanism aims to provide coordinated and integrated support to migrants, returnees, and refugees, ensuring they receive the necessary protection and services by organising and coordinating efforts among various stakeholders at different levels (International Centre for Migration Policy Development, 2024).

The NRM identifies national and international stakeholders and works with several ministries, including the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, the Ministries of Interior, Justice and Defence as well as the Kurdistan Regional Government, International Organization of Migration (IOM), the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and the European Unions (EU). These joint collaborations aim to ensure timely access to comprehensive assistance of returnees, including legal, financial, psychological, health, and education services (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Key actors of return in Iraq

2. Methodological Framework

This report relied primarily on fieldwork, surveying the opinions and experiences of returnees from EU countries, their adaptation to the life changes resulting from their transitions across multiple countries, and their levels of integration, resilience, resistance, and hope.

Two-step approval was required before conducting the field survey. First, HHRO obtained ethics clearance from the Catholic University in Erbil (Letter No. 797, dated 30 August 2023), which covered data protection aligned with EU GDRR principles. Second, HHRO secured authorisation from the Non-Governmental Organisations Directorate at the Council of Ministers' General Secretariat.¹ HHRO filed a formal request with the NGO Directorate on 23 July 2024, attaching a survey instrument jointly prepared with partners in Afghanistan, Tunisia, and Nigeria. Feedback was received on 15 August 2024, and revisions were made to ensure the questionnaire was appropriately contextualised to the Iraqi setting. For example, the education question was modified from "Did you return because education was resumed?" to "Did the quality of education improve?" since schooling had not fully stopped in Iraq. The ethnicity question was also rephrased to "What ethnic group do you belong to?" reflecting the terminology used in the constitution and the sensitivity of the topic.

In preparation for the field survey, the HHRO contacted the Migration and Displacement Ministry, as well as its international and national partners, to access returnee lists, names, and contact information. When government institutions did not cooperate as expected, in parallel HHRO relied on its partners and launched a Facebook platform in May 2024 for this purpose, allowing returnees to register and provide information about their country and year of return, place of residence, and preferred communication method. This resulted in random lists of 300

¹ The Non-Governmental Organizations Directorate is an institution affiliated with the Council of Ministers' General Secretariat. It oversees the registration and monitors the work of local and international civil society and non-governmental organizations.

returnees from 11 Iraqi governorates, most of whom had returned to the country within the past ten years, i.e., since 2014.

Facebook outreach and referrals through HHRO’s partner network generated a pool of 400 potential participants (61 identified via Facebook and 339 through partner referrals). From this pool, 300, who had returned from EU countries, met the criteria specified in the ethical approval and were selected for the survey. Of 300 returnees, 250 agreed to participated in the interviews. The remaining 50 returnees declined or withdrew from the interview, mainly because they expected personal benefits, did not attend after being contacted, had security concerns and feared potential repercussions despite assurance of confidentiality and ethical safeguards.

Map 1: Returning migrants interviewed (Geographical distribution by governorate)

HHRO stratified survey participants across major Iraqi governorates by population density, return destination and country of return. Data collection was conducted by seven enumerators, including HHRO staff and two externally hired. Ensuring balanced and representative distribution across categories was not possible due to limited cooperation from the Ministry of Migration and Displacement. This led HHRO to seek assistance from its international partners, such as IOM. Despite operational and local access constraints, HHRO could complete data collection in six governorates and conducted the survey into them, Baghdad, Nineveh, Erbil, Duhok, Sulaymaniyah, and Kirkuk. To expand geographic coverage, returnees from five additional governorates in southern Iraq were invited to Baghdad for interviews, resulted in a sample that covered 11 Iraqi governorates (see Map 1).

Due to the absence of official governorate-level data on returnees, the study used each governorate's total population as an approximate indicator to guide sample selection. Once the returnee data was generated, it became clear that participation was higher in more stable governorates; for example, Duhok had a relatively high number of returnees compared to its overall population.

From the capital Baghdad, with a population of approximately 8 million, 125 returnees were interviewed. In Nineveh, the second largest governorate (approximately 3 million), 36 returnees were interviewed; in Erbil (approximately 1.6 million), 31; in Basra (approximately 1.7 million), 4 (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of Population and Sample Size by Governorate

The sample distribution is not even; however, it is broadly proportional to the relationship between the number of returnees and the total population in each governorate, especially in Nineveh, Baghdad, and Erbil, where the ratios were similar (0.0012–0.0014–0.0019). In Duhok, where the number of returnees (especially among minorities such as Yazidis and Christians) has increased due to relative security and political stability, the sample ratio was 0.0029. In Basra and Kirkuk, where the number of returnees is small compared to Baghdad, Erbil, and Nineveh, the sample ratios were 0.0003 and 0.0002, respectively. It is necessary to

mention 16 returnees from 5 other Iraqi governorates who were interviewed in Baghdad to bring the total sample to 250, as detailed in the tables included in the report.

This disproportion stems from the small number of returnees in some governorates and their larger number in others, reflecting differences in security, stability, and economic conditions, which are analysed in other sections of this research. Although the sample of 250 returns is not strictly random, participants were randomly selected, and thus the sample provides sufficient analytical power for descriptive analysis.

The variation in sample sizes across governorates also provided scope to analyse the survey data and identify patterns in motivations for return. The majority of respondents included in the survey, approximately 93%, had returned within the past ten years, while the remainder had returned earlier.

2.2 Data Entry Mechanism

Following internal approval by the HHRO team and in coordination with the Work Package supervisors, a Microsoft Excel database was created to capture 167 questions. The database was structured to facilitate clear and accurate data entry for each respondent and to support subsequent statistical reporting.

After entering the survey responses and reviewing the dataset, the team adjusted several response categories to better reflect realities observed on the ground. For example, the initial housing question did not include options for returnees living in camps or staying with relatives – both of which frequently appeared in data. These options were added to enable accurate coding. Similar adjustments were made to other questions when needed. The questionnaire codebook was updated accordingly to ensure the dataset remained coherent and analytically usable.

Finally, data quality checks were conducted to confirm accuracy and completeness, including the identification of missing values and potential errors. The data were reviewed repeatedly by the data entry experts before proceeding to statistical analysis.

3. Demographics and Socioeconomic Status of Respondents:

The sample included returnees from 16 European countries who had returned within the last ten years (92.8%) (see Table 1).

Table 1: Share of Returnees who Returned to Iraq in the Past Ten Years

Did you return to Iraq within the past ten years?	Count	Percentage%	Mean year of return
Yes	232	92.8	2020.1
No	18	7.2	2009.1

The largest percentages of returnees were from Germany followed by Sweden, Finland, Greece, Austria, and Belgium (see Table 2).

Table 2: Share of Returnees by Country

Country	Count	Percentage (%)
Germany	122	48.8%
Sweden	31	12.4%
Finland	26	10.4%
Greece	19	7.6%
Austria	12	4.8%
Belgium	10	4.0%
France	7	2.8%
Netherlands	6	2.4%
Switzerland	5	2.0%
Bulgaria	3	1.2%
Denmark	2	0.8%
England	2	0.8%
Belarus	2	0.8%
Malta, Romania & Norway	3	1.2%

The majority of Iraqi returnees were of working age (18–60 years): 20% were aged 18–29, 36.8% were aged 30–39, 23.6% were aged 40–49, 14.4% were aged 50–59, and 5.2% were over 60 (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Age Distribution of Returnees

The respondents' average age was 38.94, with a standard deviation of 11.94. There were 204 males and 46 females, representing a ratio of 81.6% males to 18.4% females (see Table 3). Among the respondents, 38.8% of the sample were forcibly returned (see Figure 4).

Table 3: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender	Count	Percentage
Male	204	81.6%
Female	46	18.4%

Figure 4: Distribution by Type of Return

Regarding marital status, 154 of the returnees were married, 80 were single, 10 were divorced, 4 were widowed, and 2 were engaged (see Table 4).

Table 4: Distribution of Marital Status

Marital Status	Count	Percentage (%)
Single	80	32.00%
Engaged	2	0.80%
Married	154	61.60%
Widow/Widower	4	1.60%
Divorced	10	4.00%

Regarding ethnicity, Arabs were counted at 130, Kurds at 21, Chaldeans-Assyrians at 36, Turkmen at 2, and 61 people identified themselves as “others.” Most of these respondents who selected “others” were Yazidis, whom the Iraqi Constitution classifies as a religious group, although they consider themselves an ethnic group. The survey, therefore, did not include them among the ethnic groups, in accordance with the Constitution and to avoid government rejection of the survey. ⁴ The remaining respondents who did not specify their ethnicity are followers of esoteric Sufi orders who prefer not to reveal their ethnic or religious identity. ⁵ Meanwhile, Chaldeans-Assyrians are recognised in the Iraqi Constitution as ethnic minorities (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Ethnic Composition of the Sample

Of the respondents, 70 classified themselves as having completed primary education (Level 1), 63 reported having completed intermediate education (level 2), and 45 reported having completed secondary education (Level 3). Thirteen reported having completed post-secondary non-university education (Level 4), and 3 reported having completed short-term university education, known in Iraq as an institute (Level 5). Of the respondents, 32 reported having graduated with a bachelor’s degree or equivalent (Level 6), and 5 reported having obtained a master’s degree (Level 7). Fourteen respondents reported having completed some form of early childhood education, and 5 respondents identified “other” as their level of education. In short, the percentage of those with post-secondary certificates is 23.2%, and the percentage of those whose level of education is secondary or lower is 76.8% (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Education Level of Returnees

The average household size for returnees (i.e., the number of people living under one roof) was 4.84, with a standard deviation of 2.45. This rate is close to the average Iraqi family size of 5.7, according to the 2024 Iraqi census.

The maximum household size was 13 people, the minimum was 1 person, and 55 returnees reported their household size as four people.

Of the survey respondents, 154 reported being married, 4 widowed, and 88 had male dependents aged 6-18, while 88 also reported having female dependents of the same age (see Table 5).

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents with Dependent Children

Do you have any male children [aged 6-18] that are dependent on you?	Count	Percentage (%)
Yes	88	35.2
No	162	64.8
Do you have any female children [aged 6-18] that are dependent on you?	Count	Percentage (%)
Yes	88	35.2
No	162	64.8

Of the sample, 69 individuals reported being unemployed, constituting 27.6% of the total, the highest percentage, followed by elementary occupations (cleaner/labourer) at 23.6%, craft-related trades workers at 10.8%, technicians and associate professionals at 10%, managers at 5.6%, professionals at 5.2%, service and sales workers at 4.4%, clerical support workers and armed forces occupations at 4.0% each, skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers at 3.6%, and plant and machine operators and assemblers at 1.2% (see Table 5).

Table 6 shows that 61 respondents have skills, while 189 reported other occupations. Additionally, the unemployment rate in the sample was 27.6%, which is higher than Iraq's national unemployment rate of 13.5%, according to the latest Iraqi census for 2024.

Table 6: Employment Status of Respondents

Employment	Count	Percentage (%)
Managers	14	5.60%
Professional	13	5.20%
Technicians and associate professionals	25	10.00%
Clerical support workers	10	4.00%
Service and sales workers	11	4.40%
Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers	9	3.60%
Craft related trades workers	27	10.80%
Plant and machine operators, and assemblers	3	1.20%
Elementary occupations (cleaner/labourer)	59	23.60%
Armed forces occupations	10	4.00%
Unemployed	69	27.60%

Regarding skills acquired by returnees abroad and their relevance to their work in their country of origin, 198 returnees (79.2%) indicated that the skills they acquired abroad were completely unrelated to their current job. In contrast, only 13 (5.2%) reported that the skills they acquired abroad were closely related to their work. This is because many returnees face difficulties in having their professional or academic qualifications obtained abroad recognised, and the skills they acquired abroad are not compatible with the Iraqi labour market (see Table 7).

Table 7: Relevance of Skills Acquired Abroad to Returnee's Jobs in the Home Country

Are the skills you acquired abroad relevant to the job or work you are currently doing in your home country?		
Answer	Count	Percentage %
Yes, very relevant	13	5.2
Somewhat relevant	7	2.8
A little relevant	15	6
Not really relevant	17	6.8
Not relevant at all	198	79.2

Regarding business ties in the region, only 3 returnees reported having them.

As far as the sample's overall socioeconomic status, 9 participants reported having a monthly income of \$1,000 or more, 77 reported no income, 15 reported less than \$50, 50 reported between \$50 and \$200, 57 reported between \$200 and \$500, and 42 reported having an income between \$500 and \$1,000. The mean monthly income was \$268.3, and the median was \$125.2.

Only 51 participants reported above-average income, representing 20.4% of the sample, while 92 participants, representing 36.8%, were below the poverty line (see Figure 7). The average per capita income in Iraq is \$153, according to the Iraqi Planning Ministry.

Figure 7: Household Income of Respondents

Compared with the income they earned before and after their return, 168 respondents reported that their income is now lower than it was before migration (67.2%), 43 reported that it was almost unchanged, and 21 reported that they are earning more than before. The results show a significant decline in their standard of living after their return, with their situation moving towards poverty.

Furthermore, 46 respondents reported engaging in income-generating activities since their return. Of the 250 respondents, 31 reported starting a business upon their return.

Regarding satisfaction with the performance and profitability related to start-up businesses and their own economic situation, 1.6% (4 people) were very satisfied, 6% (15 people) were satisfied, 15.6% (39 people) were neutral, 13.2% (33 people) were dissatisfied, and 61.6% (154 people) were very dissatisfied.

² The income of returnees was converted from Iraqi dinars to US dollars.

In terms of their ability to meet basic financial needs, only 25 people responded “Yes, totally,” 47 participants responded “Somewhat,” 49 responded “A little,” 57 responded “Not really,” and the largest percentage, 72, responded “No, not at all.”

Regarding access to loans for business or personal purposes after returning to Iraq, only 10 of the 250 returnees reported having obtained loans to meet personal or business needs. Although the loan scheme provided by the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs is standardised for both women and men and does not vary by location, access remains limited because applicants must provide a guarantor – a government employee – who commits to repay the loan if the returnee is unable to do so.

Regarding the returnees’ housing and living conditions, responses indicated that 62 of 250 individuals owned their own homes, and that the majority (127) lived in rented units. Five respondents reported having obtained bank loans for housing, while 56 returnees described their living conditions as “other.” They gave this answer because the questionnaire did not include any reference to living with relatives or in refugee camps such as tents, caravans, or other temporary housing.

4. Countries that Iraqi Returnees hoped to Reach and Their Return Dates

Due to international sanctions on Iraq, there are no direct flights from Europe to Iraq. As a result, return routes for Iraqis usually go through neighbouring countries such as Turkey, Jordan, Iran, and others, particularly by air. For land travel, migrants have no choice but to proceed to neighbouring countries, including Syria, Turkey, Jordan, Lebanon, and Iran, and remain there until they complete their journey. Testimonies from Iraqi returnees from 11 European countries list the following destinations: Germany (122 returnees), Sweden (31), Finland (26), Greece (19), Austria (12), Belgium (10), France (7), the Netherlands (6), Switzerland (5), Bulgaria (3), Denmark, England, and Belarus (2 each), as well as Malta, Romania, and Norway (1 each). (Median = 2020, IQR = 8 years).

Regarding the number of returns by year, 2024 recorded the highest number of returnees, 55 out of 250. The sample included 24 individuals who returned in 2023, 15 in 2022, and 12 in 2025 (as of April 2025). A glance at the table (see table 8) shows that the number of returnees has increased significantly since 2015, due to the start of operations to expel terrorist groups from Iraq and the attainment of relative security and political stability in many Iraqi governorates. It is likely that the most important reasons for the increase in the number of returnees over the past ten years are the establishment of stability in Iraq during that time, the growing wave of deportation and harassment of migrants in Europe, and Iraq’s signing of bilateral agreements with a number of European countries regarding the organisation of return.

Table 8: Year of Return and Distribution in the Sample

Year of Return	Count	Percentage (%)
2025	12	4.8
2024	55	22
2023	24	9.6
2022	15	6

2021	11	4.4
2020	9	3.6
2019	14	5.6
2018	16	6.4
2017	13	5.2
2016	37	14.8
2015	23	9.2
2014	2	0.8
2013	1	0.4
2012	4	1.6
2011	2	0.8
2010	4	1.6
2009	2	0.8
2008	2	0.8
2007	2	0.8
2005	1	0.4
1992	1	0.4

5. European countries travelled to by returnees:

5.1 The Main European Countries to which Returnees Travelled or Resided

The survey showed that the sample visited a total of 23 European countries: 126 people visited Germany, 39 visited Greece, 38 visited Sweden, 30 visited Finland, 16 visited Austria, 10 visited Belgium, 8 visited France, 6 visited the Netherlands, 5 visited Bulgaria, 3 each visited Denmark and Switzerland, and 2 each visited Poland, the United Kingdom, Belarus, and North Macedonia. Norway, Italy, Romania, Ukraine, Hungary, Serbia, Lithuania, and Malta were each visited once by returnees (see Table 9).

Table 9: European Countries Travelled to by Returnees

European countries which migrants have visited /transited?	Count
Germany	126
Greece	39
Sweden	38
Finland	30
Austria	16
Belgium	10
France	8
Netherlands/Haland	6
Bulgaria	5
Denmark	3
Switzerland	3
Poland	2
United Kingdom	2
Belarus	2
North Macedonia	2
Norway	1
Italy	1
Romania	1
Ukrain	1
Hungary	1
Serbia	1
Lithuania	1
Malta	1

5.2 Total Number of Trips to European Countries

During their stay abroad, 215 individuals visited one European country; 35 returnees visited more than one: 30 visited two countries, three visited three, and one visited four. Another individual reported visiting nine European countries during their migration. These visits occurred within a single migration cycle, not multiple cycles, and this exposed the migrants to risks to their lives, as well as exploitation by smuggling networks (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Total Number of Trips Returnees had Taken to European Countries

5.3. Dates of Returnees’ Travel to Europe

A closer look at the survey participants’ travel history reveals that it began in 1991, and the average year of migration for the 250 returnees was 2014.8 (SD=5.7). Figure 9 shows the returnees’ year of travel (Minimum= 1991, Median= 2015, Maximum= 2023).

Figure 9: Dates of Returnees’ Travel to Europe

5.4 Time Spent in European Countries

The distribution of migrants by the country where they spent the most time shows that Germany (126), Sweden (38), and Finland (30) were the primary countries of residence. A smaller number of migrants spent the majority of their time in Serbia, Hungary, and Italy (one for each of them) (see Table 10).

Most respondents to the survey preferred Scandinavian and Central European countries, believing that they offer more job opportunities, have stronger economies, and provide better chances of obtaining residency and acceptance. Some countries, such as Malta, Romania, and Hungary, were considered by Iraqis to be mere transit points, in addition to the fact that the asylum application process there is complicated and takes longer. In countries such as Switzerland, the high cost of living has made it more difficult for refugees to stay there.

Table 10: Distribution of Respondents by the Country where They Spent the Most Time

Country	Frequency	Country	Frequency
Germany	126	Ukraine	1
Sweden	38	Norway	1
Finland	30	United Kingdom	2
France	8	Poland	2
Greece	39	Bulgaria	5
Austria	16	Belarus	2
Belgium	10	Lithuania	1
Denmark	3	Malta	1
Netherlands	6	Romania	1
Switzerland	3	North Macedonia	2

6. Likelihood of Future Legal and Illegal Migration:

The responses by the study population were based on the likelihood of re-migrating to another country, whether legally or illegally.

For the likelihood of legal migration, the response options ranged from 1 (very unlikely) to 5 (very likely), with 70 selecting very unlikely and 70 very likely. For the likelihood of illegal migration, the response options ranged from 1 (very unlikely) to 5 (very likely), with 175 selecting very unlikely and 40 very likely. Notably, the average response for the likelihood of legal migration was much higher than that for illegal migration, at 3.39 (SD=1.7) compared with 1.9 (SD=1.5). In other words, the number of returnees considering re-migrating to another country illegally is much lower than those considering re-migrating legally (see Figures 10 and 11).

Figure 10: Likelihood of Legal Re-Migration

Figure 11: Likelihood of Illegal Re-Migration

7. Motives for Returning to Iraq:

To understand the motivations for returning to Iraq, participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with 25 statements about the factors that prompted them to return. Table 11 and Figure 12 detail how well each statement fits the returnee's situation and reasons for returning.

As shown in the table 11, the statement "Could not obtain a visa/permanent residency in the host country" received the highest "strongly agree" score, with 122 participants responding accordingly. One participant stated that their return was due to "poor security conditions in the host country." Another stated that their return was due to "refugees forcibly being taken to war in the host country." Seventy-five participants responded, "strongly agree," and 22 agreed that their reason for returning was "Deported/Forcibly removed from the host country."

It is also noteworthy that only 9 participants strongly agreed that unemployment was the reason for their return, indicating that returnees had job opportunities in their host countries. It is further significant that a large percentage of respondents said one of the reasons for their return was their love of their homeland, with 58% agreeing to this statement and 47% strongly agreeing, yielding an average of 3.192 and a standard deviation of 1.26, indicating that patriotism and love for the homeland were strong among Iraqis (see Table 11).

Table 11: Motivation of Respondents to Return

Motivations for Return	1. Strongly disagree	2. Disagree	3. Neutral	4. Agree	5. Strongly Agree	M	SD
Could not get visa/permanent residency in host country	33	26	18	51	122	3.812	1.458991
I love my country (Patriotism)	31	42	72	58	47	3.192	1.269305
Deported/forcibly removed from host country	61	70	22	22	75	2.92	1.592985
There was no one to lead or look after our family in Iraq	67	68	21	52	42	2.736	1.467755
People of the host country were unwelcoming	57	74	48	51	20	2.612	1.25756
Feeling of racism	74	66	42	40	28	2.528	1.353963
Family reunification in Iraq	94	64	19	42	31	2.408	1.439978
Security situation in Iraq improved	62	89	48	46	5	2.372	1.103456

Feeling of marginalization	88	63	35	47	17	2.368	1.311707
Improved interactions between people in Iraq	83	72	47	43	5	2.26	1.149087
Cultural and values differences	97	64	32	45	12	2.244	1.268252
People are being treated well in Iraq	76	91	39	38	6	2.228	1.109962
Lack of integration	94	70	39	41	6	2.18	1.171153
There was no one to lead or look after our family in the host country	93	92	20	29	16	2.132	1.214321
Economic conditions in Iraq improved	85	97	30	35	3	2.096	1.057726
Unemployment in host country	119	59	32	31	9	2.008	1.193288
Because of the quality improvement of education in Iraq	118	78	33	16	5	1.848	1.008413
Poor economic conditions in the host country	132	62	27	26	3	1.824	1.062555
Drug addiction in the host country	118	91	16	19	6	1.816	1.011011
Poor security conditions in the host country	151	66	23	9	1	1.572	0.832356
Because of natural disasters in the host country	144	77	25	2	2	1.564	0.768052
Refugees are being forcibly taken to war in the host country	170	59	17	3	1	1.424	0.707265

Other Motivations: “Ambition to serve my country and community to improve their situation.” “The huge number of migrants.” “Difficult psychological situation.” “I was traumatized.” “Inhumane treatment by authorities.” “My ex-husband mistreated and abused me.” “My husband is disabled, and we didn’t get residency despite this.” “Due to a medical condition.” “For fear of my children.” “Difficulty with studying.”

8. Financial Support for Returning to Iraq:

8.1. Source of Financial Support for Return

Sixty-three returnees, representing 25.2% of the sample, reported receiving support from their host countries, while 51 (20.4%) relied on their personal savings. Notably, none of them received a loan from a bank or financial institution. Forty-nine returnees, representing 19.6%, relied on loans from family and friends. Forty-one, representing 16.4%, received funding for their return from the IOM. Only one returnee confirmed receiving support from their employer to return. The figure shows other sources of support and their percentages (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Source of Financial Support for Return

Note: Other = “Turkish Government,” “From my own work,” “Iraqi organisation,” “International Red Cross,” “German Red Cross” (2), “European Technology and Training Centre (ETTC),” “Local organisation.”

8.2. Support from Organizations as Part of Assisted Voluntary Return

Of the 250 survey participants, 60 reported receiving assistance from the IOM as part of the Assisted Voluntary Return (AVR) program, 32 from European Union countries, 21 from the UNHCR, and 16 from international and local NGOs. Eight individuals reported receiving assistance from other governments. Only one case received assistance from the Iraqi Government.

It is worth noting that 121 individuals reported receiving no assistance from any organisation or entity as part of the AVR program.

It is also noteworthy that the largest contributors to support were the IOM, European Union countries, and UNHCR (see Table 12).

Table 12: Organizational Financial Assistance as Part of Assisted Voluntary Return Program

Organization	Number of Returnees (n)	Total Expenditure (USD)	Average Expenditure PP (USD)
IOM	60	\$106,057.00	\$1,767.62
EU countries	32	\$44,383.00	\$1,386.97
Other INGO or NGO	16	\$36,200.00	\$2,262.50
UNHCR	21	\$33,300.00	\$1,585.71
Other country governments	8	\$20,960.00	\$2,620.00
Government of Iraq	1	\$205.00	\$205.00
None	121	\$0.00	\$0.00

Note: 6 returnees received financial assistance from more than one organisation.

8.3. Personal Transportation Expenses

Personal transportation expenses include airfare and ground transportation expenses. Of those surveyed, 61 (24.4%) said they did not spend any money on travel; 41 reported spending between \$1 and \$499; 85 reported spending between \$500 and \$999; 29 reported spending between \$1,000 and \$1,499; and 11 reported spending between \$1,500 and \$1,999. Twenty-three respondents (9.2%) reported spending over \$2,000 (see Figure 13). The figure shows that only about a quarter of the sample spent more than \$1,000.

Figure 13: Distribution of Amount Spent on Travel-Related Expenses for Return to Iraq

8.4. Non-Transportation Expenses

The non-transportation expenses refer to costs other than transport, such as food, beverages, and other items. Of those who participated in the survey, 84 reported spending nothing on these items, representing 33.6%. 81 respondents indicated spending between \$1 and \$199, and 50 reported spending between \$200 and \$399. Interestingly, nine respondents spent more than \$800 on these items. The figure provides further details on these (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Distribution of Amount Spent on Non-Transportation Expenses

8.5. Non-cash Support

Of the total survey participants, only nine reported receiving vocational training or specialised courses after their return, while none of them indicated that they had been assisted in finding employment or work. One person in the sample received psychosocial support and vocational training. Only three returnees reported receiving additional support beyond training, employment, and psychological support (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: Distribution of Respondents who Received Non-Cash Assistance After Returning to Iraq

Note: Other = “Logistical assistance,” “Small business,” “Buy a labor kit (wood).”

9. Treatment of Returnees at the Border

Most returnees reported that their treatment at the border and airport was good: 151 reported being treated well upon arrival, 60 reported that the treatment was acceptable, and only 39 reported that the reception was poor (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Treatment by Government Agencies Upon Arrival at National Borders

As for the issue of detention after return, the vast majority (n=231) reported not being subjected to any detention or harsh treatment upon return (see Table 13).

Table 13: Distribution of Respondents Who were Detained after Returning to Iraq

Were you detained or subjected to harsh treatment?		
Responses	Count	Percentage (%)
1. Yes	18	7.2
2. No	231	92.4
3. Don't Know	1	0.4

Regarding returnees' reception by a special immigration committee, 31 of the sample reported receiving it. In contrast, 218 reported that no specific committee received them. Only one person responded that they did not know.

Regarding whether local authorities asked about their reasons for migration, 211 responded that they were not asked, 37 reported that they were, and 2 said they did not know.

Concerning migrants being subjected to exploitation in their host country and pressure to provide information about their country of origin, 230 of the sample responded that they had not been subjected to such a question. In contrast, 19 responded “yes,” and one responded “don’t know.”

As for returnees receiving assistance from government agencies at the border, 245 of the survey participants reported receiving no assistance, while five confirmed receiving aid.

Regarding travel bans upon return, 5 of the 250 returnees reported being banned from travel. Only two of the total sample reported that their names were on the travel ban list, and only 10 reported that their passports were confiscated upon return. It is worth noting that some returnees were forcibly deported for committing violations in their host countries, whether for reasons such as not having a residence permit, or for crimes or misdemeanours they committed that they did not disclose.

The sample participants were asked whether they had received promises of job opportunities in the country upon their return, 21 respondents said they had. Regarding the actual availability of job opportunities, only 15 respondents reported receiving definite job offers upon their return.

Concerning the question of whether returnees were provided with procedures to facilitate their return to educational institutions, 230 respondents answered “no,” 15 responded “yes,” and five responded “don’t know.” It should be noted that not all returnees participating in the survey were of an age appropriate to return to educational institutions. This question may not yield the desired results, as only the youth are likely to benefit from returning to such institutions.

10. Experiences of Detention outside Country of Origin:

The majority of returnees participating in the survey were not detained for immigration-related reasons while outside their country of origin: 187 individuals reported not being detained, while 62 (24.8%) reported being detained. One individual indicated that he/she did not know (see Figure 17).

Figure 17: Detention for Migration Reasons

Thus, approximately 56% of those detained spent less than two weeks in detention while abroad, representing 14% of the sample. Those who spent more than six months in detention comprised only 3 in the total sample, representing 1.2% (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Duration of Detention Period

Finally, 48 returnees representing 19.2% of the total sample stated that their detention was related to their deportation and return procedures to Iraq.

11. Where Returnees Find Meaning in Life:

Returnees were asked about the amount of meaning they derived in life from four sources: family, friends, religious beliefs (spiritual), and work/school.

Response options for each question ranged from zero to 10, and the result was multiplied by 10 to convert it into a percentage, with zero indicating no meaning at all and 10 indicating the maximum meaning (100%). Table 14 summarises the results for each source of meaning among returnees.

Table 14: Meaning of Life

Where returnees find meaning in life						
Factor	Percentage (%)	SD	Median	IQR	Skewness	Note
Family	73.88	37.1	100%	50	-1.09	Strong negative (left-skewed) – most respondents at 100%, with a tail toward lower values
Religion and spirituality	58.92	41.8	40%	70	+0.34	Positive (right-skewed) – many give low roles to friends, with a tail toward higher values
Work/School	42.4	39.9	70%	90	-0.34	Moderate negative skew – a substantial share at high values, with a tail toward lower ones

Friends	39.8	37.4	40%	80	+0.27	Moderate positive skew – low and mid values are more common, with a minority at 80–100%
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It thus reveals that family was the most significant source of meaning for returnees, followed by religious beliefs and spirituality.

12. Coping with Life's Difficulties:

Regarding coping strategies for life difficulties, participants were asked where they seek support cope with these challenges. The answers to this is shown in Table 15, with family being the greatest source of support in facing life's difficulties, followed by spirituality, work/school, and, finally, friends at the bottom of the list. Family and spiritual adjustment is directly proportional to hope and resilience, and inversely proportional to depression. The more family and spiritual support the returnees receive, the greater their hope and resilience become, and consequently, the lower their level of depression.

Table 15: Coping with Life Difficulties

Where returnees find support to cope with life's difficulties						
Factor	Percentage (%)	SD	Median	IQR	Skewness	Note
Family	79.88	33.79	100%	20	-1.48	Very strong negative (left-skewed) – almost everyone reports extremely high family support, with only a small tail toward lower values
Religion and spirituality	57.88	42.00	40%	70	+0.28	Positive (right-skewed) – many respondents give relatively low ratings to religion and spirituality with a tail toward higher support
Work/School	41.04	39.13	70%	90	-0.33	Moderate negative skew – large share at high levels of work/school support, but with substantial variability and a tail toward low values
Friends	40.32	37.10	40%	80	+0.32	Moderate positive skew – lower and medium ratings are more common, with a minority reporting very high support from friends

Regarding friendships, the average number of close friends reported by returnees was 3.788, ranging from 0 to 5th with a standard deviation of 4.526. As for the number of acquaintances, the average was 103.8, with a minimum of 0 and a maximum of 2,000, and a standard deviation of 264.99 (Median=20, IQR=43).

In the event of a difficulty or any matter requiring immediate attention, returnees reported that family was their first point of contact, followed by friends, relatives, neighbours, and co-workers. Only nine people reported not having a support person they could turn to in the event of a difficulty. It is also noteworthy that the question allowed respondents to select more than one option (see Figure 19).

Figure 19: First Point of Contact in Case of Hardship or Urgent Matters

13. Social and Cultural Ties:

Of the total sample, 35 participants reported not attending any social or cultural events. The remaining 215 participants attended 1,374 events. These were distributed as follows: social gatherings (689), birthday parties (128), marriages (including weddings and engagements) (151), funerals (233), sightseeing trips (155), and other ceremonies, such as attending a national celebration or entertainment event (18) (see Table 16).

Table 16: Distribution of Respondents Attending Social or Cultural Events in Iraq

	Social gathering Party	birthday party	Marriage (including wedding, engagement)	Funeral	travel for sightseeing	Other ceremony	None
Total persons	139	78	87	100	70	9	35
total instances	689	128	151	233	155	18	-

14. Hope, Resilience, and Depression among Returnees

Returnees reported moderate levels of hope, resilience, and depression. Figure 20 shows the levels of hope among returnees. The instrument used to measure refugees' hope (Snyder et al., 1991) comprised 12 items associated with higher optimism about life and the pursuit of goals, alongside minimal worry about one's outlook (Appendix 1).

Response options ranged from "strongly disagree" (1) to "strongly agree" (5), with a minimum of 1.58 and a maximum of 4.92. The overall mean level of hope was 3.53. The standard deviation was 0.47, indicating that the sample was more hopeful than pessimistic.

Figure 20: Distribution of Respondents' Hope Level

As for hope after returning to Iraq, 123 of those who returned were not happy about their previous migration, compared to 81 who were. This indicates that the majority had bitter experiences during their journey that do not bring them happiness when they recall them, and that their return may restore hope (see Figure 21).

Figure 21: Distribution of Respondents' Level of Happiness with Return

Responses to the statement “I regret my previous migration” showed that 31.2% of the sample strongly disagreed, 29.6% disagreed, 8.4% strongly agreed, 18% agreed, and 12.8% were neutral. This indicates that the majority of returnees did not regret their previous migration (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: Distribution of Respondents’ Level of Dissatisfaction of Previous Migration

Figure 23 shows that the returnees’ responses to the statement “I regret my return and intend to migrate again” tended toward regretting their return and considering migrating again.

Figure 23: Distribution of Respondents' Level of Dissatisfaction of Return and Intention for Re-Migration

The responses presented in Figures 24 and 25 reveal a discrepancy. While 47.2% of respondents reported they could rebuild their lives in Iraq, 36% said they felt hopeful after returning, compared with 39.2% who reported feeling no hope. Overall, this suggests that post-return hope is slightly lower than the absence of hope, indicating a moderate, though fragile, level of optimism among returnees.

Figure 24: Distribution of Respondents' Level of Optimism about Starting a New Life in Iraq

Figure 25: Distribution of Respondents' Level of Hope after Returning to Iraq

15- Resilience

Figure 26 presents a visual of the distribution of responses regarding returnees' resilience. The response options for each item ranged from "strongly disagree" (1) to "strongly agree" (5), with the minimum response value being 1 and the maximum one being 5. Returnees reported an average resilience score of 3.76 (standard deviation = 0.61), indicating a moderate level of resilience (see Appendix 2).

Figure 26: Distribution of Respondents' Resilience Level

16- Depression

To estimate returnee depression, we used the 10-item scale by Björgvinsson et al. (2013). The scale captured returnees' lack of focus, feelings of restlessness and inertia, and fear (see Appendix 3 for details). Following conventions in research practice, the response scores ranged from "rarely or never" (0) to "always or all the time" (3). The lowest level of depression reported by participants was 0, while the highest level reported was 3. The scale's average was 1.14, with a standard deviation of 0.69. It can therefore be said that of the 250 returnees surveyed, 32.8% suffer from depression symptoms (see Figure 27).

Figure 27: Distribution of Respondents Depression Level

As a result, the correlations among the three scales—hope, resilience, and depression—are consistent with theoretical expectations regarding their interactions. The moderate association between hope and depression and the weaker link between resilience and depression, combined with the strong correlation between hope and resilience, suggest that both hope and resilience serve as psychological protective factors. However, hope appears to play a more dominant role in buffering against depressive symptoms within this sample.

The strong relationship between hope and resilience ($r = 0.677$) points to a notable conceptual overlap between the two constructs. Further partial correlation analyses demonstrate that hope accounts for most of the unique protective variance typically attributed to resilience. These findings align with the expected measurement characteristics, data distribution patterns, and underlying psychological mechanisms that differentiate the constructs (see Figure 28).

Figure 28: Correlation between Hope and Resilience

17. Returnees' Health

Most returnees reported positive health: 54 reported excellent health, 39 very good health, 74 good health, 30 poor health, and 53 somewhat good health (see Figure 29).

Figure 29: Returnees' Health Status

18. Conclusion and Recommendations

This report sheds light on the conditions of Iraqi returnees, their difficult reality, the circumstances they have endured, their experiences, the motivations for their return, and their return paths. It draws on data from 250 individual participants from 11 Iraqi governorates surveyed in 6 locations (governorates). The survey was conducted in six major Iraqi governorates with the highest rates of return: Baghdad, Nineveh, Erbil, Duhok, Kirkuk, and Sulaymaniyah. The survey also covered the religious and ethnic diversity of the Iraqi social fabric.

Since detailed statistics on returnees, broken down by gender and distributed across Iraqi governorates, are unavailable, interviews were conducted with returnees who participated in the survey in larger governorates. The higher number of applicants from a particular governorate suggests a larger number of returnees there. Furthermore, the sample was not gender-balanced. However, it is well-known in Iraq that the majority of migrants are male, fleeing the oppression of dictatorial regimes and the ongoing wars and instability. It is natural, therefore, that the number of male returnees would exceed that of female returnees. Due to the lack of official statistics detailing the numbers of male and female returnees, it is impossible to calculate a percentage of female returnees in the survey, as there are no official figures available for female returnees in Iraq. It should be noted that the latest Iraqi census for 2024 showed that the proportion of females is close to that of males (50.2% males and 49.8% females), but this is not reflected in the issue of return, given that the number of female returnees in the sample reached 46, ten of whom returned forcibly and 36 voluntarily, married (29), single (9), widow (4) and divorced (4) with an average age (40.6) years old (maximum age 85 and minimum 18).

The results reveal a multifaceted and multidimensional return and integration experience, often associated with numerous challenges, not without risk and danger. Returnees are characterised by social vulnerability and economic decline, high levels of psychological distress, limited financial and in-kind (non-cash) support, difficulties accessing basic services such as housing, food, and healthcare, and restricted access to employment and loans for business or personal purposes. Whether those returning had done so voluntarily or involuntarily, their cultural and educational levels, as well as ethnic, regional, and sectarian affiliations, varied. This reinforces the view that migration was driven by economic and security concerns, as well as by frustration with Iraq's continued political instability.

While the results revealed moderate levels of hope and resilience, depression and anxiety about the future persist among a third of returnees. This combination of hope and moderate resilience, alongside noticeable depressive symptoms, is reasonable in the context of reintegration in difficult and restrictive circumstances, where resilience enables the coexistence required for adaptation despite depressive symptoms. This is a contextual duality, not a contradiction.

There is a significant need for psychosocial support, especially since a quarter of the total number surveyed reported experiencing detention abroad, with 75% of those experiencing deportation and the profound psychological trauma that resulted. Most of those who returned did so because they were unable to secure permanent residence in the host country or were forcibly displaced.

While most returnees were well-received upon arrival, the results also show that integration is severely hampered by the limited assistance they receive, whether financial, access to employment, training, rehabilitation, or psychosocial support. The results also reveal that more than 95% did not receive any non-cash assistance, such as training, psychosocial rehabilitation, or employment support. There is a high level of financial distress and unemployment, as well as housing difficulties, with more than 70% of returnees living in rented homes, camps, or with relatives. They also face difficulties in the camps, and even those who stayed with relatives felt humiliated, while some were subjected to inappropriate

treatment. Approximately 75% reported that their income had decreased upon their return, compared to before their migration, and more than 70% expressed difficulty meeting their basic living needs. Approximately three-quarters of the returnees in the sample were dissatisfied with their overall situation, and only 12% were able to start a business to continue their new life in their country of origin. The fact that more than 60% of returnees are dissatisfied with the profitability of their business projects requires the Iraqi government and relevant actors to follow up on these projects and support them to ensure their success and sustainability.

Although the results demonstrate that family, spiritual values and religious beliefs play a supportive role in helping returnees move forward psychologically and socially, and integrate, they are certainly insufficient given the limited and weak institutional assistance, as well as ineffective social and economic support mechanisms, which further complicate the returnees' situation and exacerbate their suffering and vulnerability.

Despite the development of Iraq's institutional and legal framework for return policies since 2015, the presence of the Migration and Displacement Ministry as the direct executive institution responsible for migration, return, and asylum, Iraq's accession to the Global Compact for Migration (2018), the launch of the National Strategy for Migration Management (2020), the establishment of a National Referral Mechanism to support returnees in 2023, and the presence of a ministerial coordination committee to receive returnees, implementation and coordination remain weak, particularly with regard to integration programs, allocations, and government financial support provided in this regard. There are significant gaps in coordination among government institutions, as well as in coordination with relevant international and local institutions. There are also gaps in providing adequate, sustainable economic opportunities and financial support, both from host countries and from the country of origin (Iraq), to protect returnees' human rights and dignity.

In this context, the report reveals the poverty and vulnerability experienced by returnees, especially the decline in their income, which has negatively affected their integration and increased their intention to remigrate. Despite the financial support provided by numerous organisations, such as the IOM and UNHCR, this assistance is considered temporary and emergency. In contrast, support should be grounded in a strategic framework that ensures a sustainable economic situation until integration is achieved and the returnees' livelihoods improve.

Given the weak financial support and the lack of social and psychological support reported by returnees, coupled with the ongoing political and economic instability in the country, high prices, and high inflation, returnees are forced to either consider remigration or reluctantly adapt, shattering their hopes of moving forward. For many of them, resilience and perseverance are not a path to progress and recovery, but rather merely an attempt to survive, further fuelling anxiety about the future and depression.

The research identified a reality, unanimously agreed upon by the research sample, regarding the human rights violations accompanying the detention and return of the affected groups. These violations are often described as "voluntary," but in reality, they are coercive and disrespectful of individual rights. This is due to the immigration and security authorities' practices against those deported to their countries, and the particular discrimination involved. Fieldwork also revealed that some deportees were not allowed to consult lawyers, be brought before the judiciary, or exhaust all avenues for appeal and review of their cases. The principle of family unity was also not respected during deportation, as the focus was on deportation rather than other humanitarian concerns.

The indicators revealed by the report through fieldwork and survey results necessitate targeted, organised, rights-based interventions that meet returnees' basic needs and support their sustainable integration, protecting their security and dignity.

19. Recommendations:

1. Strengthen commitment to human rights in the context of the return of migrants and forcibly deported persons, ensuring it is safe and dignified.
2. Ensure that forcibly deported persons or voluntary returnees receive sufficient financial support to cover the costs of starting a new life and reintegration in their country of origin, by providing financial resources to organise forced or voluntary return movements, provided that individuals or families to be deported are notified at least six months in advance and that they are enrolled in awareness-raising courses on return and returnee rights, both in the host country and that of origin. This will help alleviate some of the negative psychological distress experienced by returnees after losing everything they owned.
3. Call upon the European Union and international organisations to cooperate and coordinate effectively with the Migration and Displacement Ministry to strengthen its operational capacity to develop the NRM for returnees, to create more effective governance, and to ensure that returnees and forcibly deported persons enjoy access to basic services such as healthcare, education, and housing. In this context, the performance of National Referral Program staff should be improved to ensure they are better equipped to deal with returnees, the necessary funds should be allocated to protecting returnees' rights, and coordination between the European Union and Iraq in supporting training and psychosocial treatment programs for returnees as a priority for their reintegration.
4. Urge the Iraqi Government, the European Union, and international organisations to increase financial allocations and budgets to support returnees after their return to Iraq (origin country) by providing basic necessities such as housing, clothing, education, and health services, and to provide adequate support for families with children, the elderly, and widows.
5. Urge the Iraqi Government to engage civil society organisations, as well as religious and social institutions, to support the returnees' reintegration process.
6. Organising a clear, and transparent agreements by both the host country and the country of origin and to strengthen the existed bilateral and regional agreements to create joint cooperation to implement the return process in a responsible and humane manner, so that returnees are treated in a way that preserves their dignity, regardless of the circumstances and reasons that prompted their migration.
7. Urge the Iraqi Government to expand vocational training for returnees, while activating private-sector institutions' roles in integrating them into available jobs and capitalising on the experience gained during their migration by supporting their livelihood, facilitate loans, and encourage small business initiatives, especially for youth and women, especially those who provide for their families, in finding work or employment, as well as people with disabilities, and support children and youth in returning to education and study.

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21. Appendix:

1. Hope Scale

No.	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
HopeQ1a	I can think of many ways to get out of a jam.					
HopeQ1b	I energetically pursue my goals.					
HopeQ1c	I feel tired most of the time. [R]					
HopeQ1d	There are lots of ways around any problem.					
HopeQ1e	I am easily downed in an argument. [R]					
HopeQ1f	I can think of many ways to get the things in life that are important to me.					
HopeQ1g	I worry about my health. [R]					
HopeQ1h	Even when others get discouraged, I know I can find a way to solve the problem.					
HopeQ1i	My past experiences have prepared me well for my future.					
HopeQ1j	I've been pretty successful in life.					

HopeQ1k	I usually find myself worrying about something. [R]					
HopeQ1l	I meet the goals that I set for myself.					
<i>Note: R = reversed.</i>						

2- Resilience Scale

No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
[MigQ10nh1]	I am able to adapt when changes occur.					
[MigQ10h2]	I can deal with whatever comes my way.					
[MigQ10nh3]	I try to see the humorous side of things when I am faced with problems.					
[MigQ10nh4]	Having to cope with stress can make me stronger.					
[MigQ10nh5]	I tend to bounce back after illness, injury or other hardships.					
[MigQ10nh6]	I believe I can achieve my goals, even if					

	there are obstacles.					
[MigQ10nh7]	Under pressure, I stay focused and think clearly.					
[MigQ10nh8]	I am not easily discouraged by failure.					
[MigQ10nh9]	I think of myself as a strong person when dealing with life's challenges and difficulties .					
[MigQ10nh10]	I am able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger.					

3- Depression Scale

No.	Statements	Rarely or none of the time (less than 1 day)	Some or a little of the time (1-2 days)	Occasionally or a moderate amount of time (3-4 days)	All of the time (5-7 days)
DepressionQ1a	I was bothered by things that usually don't bother me.				
*DepressionQb	I had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing.				

DepressionQ2c	I felt depressed.				
DepressionQ2d	I feel that everything I do is an effort to remain alive.				
DepressionQ2e	I am optimistic and hopeful about the future [R].				
DepressionQ2f	I felt fearful.				
DepressionQ2g	My sleep was restless.				
DepressionQ2h	I was happy [R].				
DepressionQ2i	I felt lonely.				
DepressionQ2j	I could not "get going."				
<i>Note:</i> R = reversed.					

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